

BREVI NOTE / SHORT NOTES

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NEW ITALIAN RECORDS OF *CALOSOMA (CAMINARA) OLIVIERI* (Coleoptera
Carabidae) FOR THE ISLANDS OF THE SICILIAN CHANNEL

Nuovi reperti per l'Italia di Calosoma (Caminara) olivieri (Coleoptera Carabidae) nelle isole del Canale di Sicilia

Calosoma (Caminara) olivieri Dejean, 1831 is a ground beetle Carabidae of the genus *Calosoma* subgenus *Caminara*, very similar to *Calosoma (Campalita) algiricum* Géhin, 1885 and *Calosoma (Campalita) maderae* (Fabricius, 1775). It is distributed across a very wide area from the Atlantic coast of Africa to India and Central Asia without significant changes in its morphology, and in fact it is considered monotypic (BRUSCHI, 2013). It is known from the Azores, the Canaries and Cabo Verde islands, is present across northern Africa from the Mediterranean coast at the northern edge of the Sahara and in Egypt (www.calosomas.com; BRUSCHI, 2013). As an occasional visitor, *C. olivieri* has been found in Spain (BRANES, 1990; SERRANO, 2003) and in the Maltese Islands (MIFSUD & VIGNA TAGLIANTI, 1999). In Italy only two previous records were known: one specimen found in the island of Lampedusa (VIGNA TAGLIANTI, 1995) and one specimen found in Palermo (SPARACIO, 2003). In this short note I report the third and fourth records for Italy, obtained at Pantelleria and at Linosa Islands, Pelagic (Agrigento, Sicilian Channel, Sicily). At Pantelleria Island, field observations were conducted primarily in spring, and exactly over the period April 20th to May 20th of the years 2004-2012, on behalf of LIPU. Moreover, in 2005, a visit was conducted during October 15th to 22nd. In 2008, observations were made during the period August 20th to September 20th, again on behalf of LIPU. In the last fifteen years (2005-2019), Linosa has been visited annually by a group of birdwatchers (MISC) in autumn and spring. In addition to ornithological researches, numerous entomological and malacological studies have also been carried out by members of the group in the Pelagic islands, during which several new records for the Pelagic islands, for Sicily, for Italy and even for Europe and the Western Palearctic were made (CORSO, 2011a, 2011b; CORSO *et al.* 2012, 2017; CORSO & VIGANÒ, 2019; COLONNELLI *et al.*, 2016; CASALINI *et al.*, 2017; LIBERTO *et al.*, 2017; VIGANÒ *et al.*, 2017; JANNI *et al.*, 2020). During the overall visits to Linosa, that totaled almost two years of field researches, we walk all around the island on a daily base: the main attention is devoted to bird migration and to dragonflies, but search for malacofauna and entomofauna have also a relevant part. In May 2009, I found 1 ♀ of *C. olivieri* just out in the garden of the rented house at Bugeber, Pantelleria (Fig.1). The specimen was still alive although in bad condition. It was collected and preserved with a lot of other entomological specimens. Later on, it was sent to Marcello Romano from Palermo, who first identified correctly the specimen. The news was spread on the webpage www.entomologiitaliani.net, and cited by S. Bruschi as by M. Romano (2010) in his webpage *Calosomas of the World* (www.calosomas.com).

Fig. 1 — The female *Calosoma (Caminara) olivieri* Dejean, 1831 found at Pantelleria Island (Agrigento, Sicilian Channel) in May 2009 (Photo by M. Romano).

In October 2019, I found 1♂ at Linosa, in the southern part of the island, dead under one light of the houses facing the sea over the harbour of Via ScaloVecchio.

The distinction from *C. algiricum* and *C. maderae* is not strightward and require great attention: *C. olivieri* compared to the two similar cited species, it is characterized by a small, just transverse, pronotum. The elytral sculpture consists of scaly intervals not much raised but recognizable; these are all of the same width and height (“homodyname” type) and there are two tertiary intervals on each sides of a secondary one (“pentaploïde” type) (“triploïde” in the other two species). In addition, the median tibiae are sub-rectilinear and in the male the first three anterior tarsomeri are dilated (SPARACIO, 2003). For what concern the arrival of this ground-beetle in Sicily, as reported by SPARACIO (2003), it is a powerful flier, that favored by southern winds (as Scirocco and Libeccio) may reach Sicily in flight or using also passive means of transport such as sealing boats or ferries and then fly before landing or just after the boats have landed. In the case of Pantelleria, it is likely that the imago arrived over the Island on its own, while at Linosa it could have arrived using passive transports; in fact, a few days earlier, some fishing boats from the southern part of the Sicilian Channel approached the island (one from Tunisia). However, the fact that the imago was found under the lights of the harbor, could also means that the insect arrived on its own flying and was attracted by the lights, as often reported for this species and other *Calosoma* sp. (MONASTRA, 1984; BRANES, 1990; SERRANO, 2003; SPARACIO, 2003).

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